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CLUSTER MANAGEMENT TECHNOLOGY AND ITS IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract: This article is aimed at ensuring the socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, employment of various segments of the population and increasing their incomes. In the study, the system from the cultivation of the product to its processing in the network-desert-pastoral animal husbandry, which is one of the unique branches of agriculture, was studied. In addition, the need to introduce into the production of cluster management technology, which combines the life experience and knowledge of scientists and industry professionals, economists and economists, further developing the sub-complex.

Keywords: desert-pastoralism, cluster, processing, costs, benefits.

I. INTRODUCTION

There are a number of factors that hinder the effective use of the market mechanism in the sub-complex of desert-pastoral livestock. In particular, research shows that service enterprises are underdeveloped, and the demand of farms for services is not sufficiently met. A healthy competitive environment has not yet been formed in these areas, the organization of modern alternative and non-governmental forms of service enterprises and the attraction of the necessary investments are not at the required level. Reasons such as the transformation of companies into farms, the transition to diversified production lead not only to a sharp increase in demand for agricultural services, but also to the need to improve the process of diversification in this system. Indeed, in the current situation, the timely satisfaction of producers' demand for quality and affordable agricultural services remains a serious problem, which in turn has a negative impact on the introduction of market mechanisms and sustainable development and competitiveness of the industry.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following scholars have considered cluster management technology and its improvement in their research: Kayumov F.K. [1], Ibragimov Yu. [2], Tangirov A.E. [3], [4], Fayzieva Sh.Sh. [5].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the implementation of the study, the conclusions and recommendations are formed as a result of the analysis of indicators of effective development of communication services through economic methods. In addition, the method of analysis and synthesis was used effectively in the conduct of scientific research.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

21.0 mln. with more than a hectare of pastures, their efficient use depends in many respects on the development of desert pastoralism. However, instead of satisfying the demand for fodder of karakul sheep at least 85% from pastures, only 50-55% will be spent on average 21-22 thousand soums more per head, production funds will be 60-65% obsolete, and only 30% of ewes will be artificially inseminated. does not allow for sustainable development.

One zoo-veterinary point serves 48.4 thousand heads or 4-6 times more conditioned sheep instead of 8.0-12.0 thousand conditional sheep, depending on the size of the area where the livestock is located. Kashkadarya region allocates \$ 33.0 million for veterinary services received orders worth 27.0 million soums. soums or 81.7%. The cost of veterinary services for one head of sheep in the country amounted to 80.0 soums instead of 15.0 thousand soums. In addition, despite the fact that more than half of the country's population lives in rural areas, the volume of services here has not exceeded 25-27 percent in the last year. In the regions where the karakul industry is located, the level of supply is 10-15 times lower than in other sectors of agriculture in the country.

In addition, the lack of processing capacity of the main part of the products, the fact that products such as sheep's milk, cow hides and wool are almost not used, and most of the products are sold as raw materials without deep processing, leads to a

sharp decline in competitiveness. For example, in Navoi region, meat processing does not exceed 18-20%, wool 21-21%, and hides 30%. Karakol leather processing is completed by washing, and wool by washing. The production of finished products from them is almost non-existent. As a result, the marketability of wool was 66.9%, astrakhan leather - 34.7% and cattle skins - 9.9%, and 2,783.7 tons of wool, 3,649 pieces of astrakhan leather and 15,775 pieces of cattle skins were not found.

So, one of the factors limiting the sustainable development of desert-pastoral farms is the problem of selling their products. Studies have shown that there is a strong demand for deep-processed products that are not raw materials in the domestic market as well as in the foreign market. Small enterprises operating in the cities of Bukhara, Turtkul, Nurata and some farms produce 4-5 times more income from the production of desert livestock products and sell them in domestic and foreign markets. In the neighboring Republic of Kazakhstan, before the launch of the wool processing plant, 1 kg of raw wool was sold for 5 tenge only when a buyer was found. Now it is 1 kg. the selling price of coarse wool has risen to 18 tenge.

Studies show that 62.4% of the costs for the production of finished products from astrakhan leather were spent on its production, 37.6% on processing. However, with 37.6 per cent of the cost of processing karakul leather, the manufacturer of the finished product is making 86.7 per cent of the profit, while the manufacturer of the product is making only 13.3 per cent. For meat processing, the processor spent only 11.2% of the profits at a cost of 73.2%, while the processor received 88.8% of the profits at a cost of 26.8%. The wool processor spent only 13.3 percent of production costs, absorbing 86.9 percent of the profits. This means that processing enterprises, as an independent business entity, using the most important monopoly position, are unjustifiably misappropriating 70-75% of the income of production farms.

Along with the above, major problems such as the lack of a system of training qualified personnel for the sub-complex of desert-pastoral livestock, unsatisfactory research and breeding, lack of marketing (sales) services, interrelated organizational

and economic interdependence, especially development and market services, , can be solved by the introduction of cluster management technology, which combines the activities of enterprises, enterprises, farms that process raw materials, sell finished products, provide services for the training of scientific and highly qualified personnel.

Finding a reasonable solution to existing problems requires teamwork. Ensuring sustainable development is inconceivable without effective integration of education, science and industry, without innovative processes. This is because innovation is the product of active cooperation of research, science, education and industry, starting from the idea that knowledge is the result of fully concentrated integration, a prosperous and prosperous life based on renewal, a factor of social and economic growth.

To this end, radically improve the system of training highly qualified personnel for the desert-pastoral livestock complex, a stable system of training, retraining and advanced training of secondary special specialists together with zooengineering, veterinary, engineering-technological, engineering-technical specialists in accordance with world standards. need to be created.

In an economy, a cluster means not only competition, but also the formation of a group of manufacturing enterprises and organizations united in a technological system based on stable socio-economic relations and mutually trusting cooperation based on active knowledge exchange, effective use of existing raw materials, energy and labor resources.

A system that ensures socio-economic development, gradually increases employment and real incomes of various segments of the population, from the cultivation of unique sectoral-pastoral livestock to deep processing, further development of the sub-complex, scientists, production specialists, economists it is expedient to introduce cluster management technology that combines experience, skills, knowledge.

In Bukhara region, the investment in the cluster of industrial processing of sheep wool, organized in the form of "Komteks pposy" LLC, managed by the local government, will be directed mainly to the expansion and modernization of existing spinning, weaving and sewing and knitting facilities. The complex will supply 1.5 million units a year to domestic and foreign markets . pieces of finished product, 2.5 thousand tons of yarn, about 4 mln. pogono meter allows the delivery of textile products. However, along with wool, unique karakul leather, meat, sheep skins, milk and other products are obtained from karakul sheep.

It is desirable to cover the sub-complex of balik desert-pastoral livestock in a single cluster, not by a separate product type. This is due to the fact that, firstly, astrakhan skin, wool, meat, milk and sheep skins are obtained from karakul sheep, but also products from goat, cattle, camel, horse, poultry, and secondly, the formation of a cluster on only one product type processing does not ensure the transformation of the finished product into a product, thirdly, the cluster leads to the inevitable disruption of production technology due to the transfer of the bulk of economic resources to the type of product in which it is organized. The management of the cluster is carried out by a special coordinating council formed of highly qualified specialists. It is advisable that this board consists of groups for each type of finished product produced in the cluster area. The Council is responsible for developing a strategy for future sustainable socio-economic development of the Desert-Pasture Livestock Cluster and coordinating its implementation.

In the area covered by the cluster will be organized the development and introduction of high-efficiency equipment and technologies, research institutions related to the solution of scientific and practical problems, training of highly qualified specialists by higher and secondary special education institutions. Growing the seeds of desert-pasture plants and ensuring the increase of pasture productivity (instead of 2.5-3.0 ts / ha) by 20-25 ts / ha on the basis of innovative technologies and forming a water supply system, fodder preparation, processing, veterinary

services , the establishment of enterprises engaged in shearing sheep, slaughtering lambs for astrakhan skin, processing meat, wool, astrakhan skins, cow hides, sheep and other dairy products, and producing and selling finished goods. As a result, thousands of new jobs will be created, and incomes will increase 4-5 times, which will create opportunities for sustainable socio-economic development of the region, as well as increase the competitiveness of the desert pasture complex.

The introduction of cluster technology of management ensures the production of high value-added products, which in turn controls all joints of the complex using a system of intelligent machines, which is very cheap than water, which dramatically reduces production costs (1 l. 300 soums) can be used to generate and introduce energy, biogas production and other similar technologies . The resulting profit will increase several times and further strengthen the competitiveness of the complex.

V. CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

It is expedient to introduce cluster management technology that ensures the sustainable development of desert-pastoral animal husbandry, namely:

- coverage of the sub-complex of balik desert-pastoral livestock in one cluster, not by separate product type;
- cluster management is carried out by a special coordinating council formed of highly qualified specialists;
- we shall recommend that the profits be distributed in accordance with the contribution of the enterprises of the cluster to the finished product.

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